

CST4ALL

Support to the Activities of the Concentrated Solar Thermal Technology Area of the SET Plan

Online Workshop Meteorology for renewable energy technologies

Date and time	December 11, 2024 – 10:00 AM – 12:00 PM CET
Venue	Online (via MS Teams)
Free Registration	CST4ALL website or MS Teams website

The analysis of the current state of the art of meteorology for solar and other renewable energy technologies as well as the research work being carried out for these technologies sets the ground to identify what needs to be done to support the energy goals in Europe. An accurate knowledge of the actual meteorological conditions as well as the conditions expected in the short, medium and large term are key to enable the correct planning and assure an optimal operation of renewable energy systems, for which the input energy source is variable in nature.

By bringing together leading experts in the field of CST, PV, wind and other renewable energy technologies, both from industry and research institutions, **this workshop aims to identify joint research areas, benefit from the knowledge and tools of the different sectors and inform the public about the capabilities currently available in Europe and how it is expected that these will evolve.**

Agenda

10:00	Opening remarks Peter HELLER, DLR
10:05	Introduction to the workshop, the project and its relevance to the European policy on renewable energy research Philippe SCHILD, EC RTD Unit
10:10	SSH and gender issues in the CST4ALL project Yelda ERDEN-TOPAL, METU, Türkiye
10:15	Session 1: State of the art and running research
10:15	State of the art of meteorology for solar technologies and further renewable energy systems Alberto TROCCOLI, WEMC

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101075408.

10:30	Current meteo research for solar/CST and links to other RE technologies Manuel SILVA, University of Seville
10:45	Current meteo research for wind energy and links to other RE technologies Andrea N. HAHMANN, DTU
11:00	Session 2: Research needs for specific RE technology and topic and link to other RE technologies
11:00	Wind resource assessment, monitoring and forecasting Corinna MÖHRLÉN, WEPROG
11:15	Solar resource assessment, monitoring and forecasting Jan REMUND, Meteotest
11:30	Live poll on importance of research topics for solar and wind energy systems and collection and prioritization of questions from the audience
11:35	Roundtable on synergies and discussion All speakers, moderated by Stefan Wilbert, DLR
11:55	Wrap-up and Conclusions Peter HELLER, DLR
12:00	End of the workshop

CST4ALL team reserves the right to make changes to the workshop program.

CST4ALL Coordinator

**Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.**
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum Fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101075408.